

The Role of Hand Drawing in Logo Design in Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: Hand-painted art in the world and Vietnam with its long-standing origins always evolves with the flow of human civilization. With the diverse development of fine arts, hand drawing does not stand on the sidelines but always promotes its potential in life applications, contributing to promoting human aesthetic awareness. Only through hand drawing can the form and content of symbols vividly, delicately, and specifically reflect their object of reflection. This article surveys the process of creating some logos, symbols of some typical objects in Vietnam, through which, tries to clarify the role of hand drawing in the formation of quality of these products symbol is formed. In particular, through research results, it can be affirmed that hand drawing will still play an important role in artistic creativity despite the explosion of technology and the development of artificial intelligence.

KEYWORDS: hand drawing, the role of hand drawing, icons, logo design, Vietnamese fine arts.

1. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam, with a tradition of handicraft villages and skillful and sophisticated hands, after the French opened art schools, created a generation of talented artists serving the advertising industry. The report contributes to improving people's aesthetic life. After liberation, in 1975, with a subsidized economy, paintings, books, and newspapers still developed promoting revolutionary policies and building the country in entirely hand-drawn forms. The country's period of innovation has brought a fresh breeze to the art of advertising, and as the country integrates with the market economy, the Graphic Design industry is gradually catching up with world trends, with motto of integrating but not dissolving. Vietnam gradually shapes trends and maintains national traditions through hand-painted crafts. Advertising companies with dedicated designers always complete the process with the first steps always starting with a hand-drawn sketch of the general idea, from there going to the details and on the machine to complete the work.

2. RESEARCH STATUS OF THE TOPIC

Jacques Derrida, through deconstruction theory, argued that drawing and theory are intrinsically linked, which has led to continuous reflection on the relationship between thinking and drawing, on how specific means of expression may be related to specific conceptions of space. Jacques Derrida clarified this aspect of drawing, focusing on the relationship between the eye and the hand. Derrida compares drawing to writing and sees "anticipation" as an "anticipated grasp," that is, a touch toward the unknown, as the most basic act of drawing. Taking this reasoning to an extreme, led Derrida to consider both drawing itself and the act of drawing as 'blind'. The drawing becomes a graph leading into the abyss, where it is not a summary interpretation in external iconography, but the rational subjective expression of an internal vision. From Derrida's arguments, the author further explores the subjective skill of the painter through his main organ, which is his hands. Brings an overall, harmonious look between internal and external elements through the creativity of the artist's hands.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article uses the method of observing hand drawings and even machine drawings in the formation of logos and symbols. After observing, the author will analyze each drawing sample, clarifying the superiority of hand drawing in the formation of its products. The author also uses the comparative method to clarify the difference in value brought by hand drawing compared to not using hand drawing in artistic creation.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The symbol has become a factor in human civilized life, becoming a special sign representing an object or event, and up to now it has grown to become a symbol representing a company company, organization, person, service or idea. A recognizable symbol that confirms the origin of goods becomes a legally copyrighted trademark for goods made by a specific company in which the art of hand-painting is involved right from the start form initial ideas.

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When a business, company, organization, individual or group wants to develop its activities, it wants to find its own logo that represents its own image through which to send messages. A message we hope everyone will accept. Therefore, logos are an important job of Graphic Design. In 2014, Ho Chi Minh City University of Culture decided to change the school's logo to replace the old logo, although it still represents the meaning of the image of books and musical notes as one of the school's training fields. But because of that, it becomes too detailed and easily resembles some other logos in the same field, directing the viewer to a vague overall image, lacking the modernity of the country's innovation period. (Figure 1). The final selected work, composed by artist Do Van Dung, brings a new image, in a minimalist style - simplified in accordance with the trend of the times as well as visualizing the meaning of the school with a plaque. Modern shapes are highly evocative (Figure 2).

The new logo represents the idea by using the main image of an open book, placed in a closed circle representing durability. It is also the combination of the letters V and H, which stands for the school's training major, Culture. The book represents general ideas for the school's training field. The image of the book opening like a blooming flower represents aspiration and success in a training career. With the dark blue tone as the main color of the logo, it is the trend of using colors in the training field. The meaning of this color represents intelligence, aspiration, belief and sustainability, and is highly professional.

A rough sketch is the initial step of each design stage, describing the structure and layout. This is not a complete design from color to overall design. The sketch is just a descriptive example short. Artist Do Van Dung's idea for sketching the logo here is based on the educational career of the University of Culture as well as the school's aspirations in its hundred-year work of cultivating people. From there, he hand-sketched hundreds of different designs in his sketchbook. Then, select and refine the image and add details. This step will be repeated with a pen and eraser until the most complete model is created. In the end, the artist produces 10 models. Most suitable for certain styles and images such as trees, color palettes, lotus flowers, bird wings, etc. to create the most meaningful symbol, but in general, it's all about the spirit of modernity modern, streamlined in the way of creating pieces and lines. The final work is re-selected through about two revisions to be as perfect as possible (Figure 3).

To create the V and H shapes, the artist cannot use a font available on the computer to combine but must rely on a hand-drawn board to create an abstract image with harmonious, soft lines but still ensuring the rigidity and solemnity required of a university. Thanks to the meticulous refinement and adjustment of every detail in the hand-drawing stage, the artist creates shapes that are both emotional but also carry profound design principles, in which Eastern philosophy shapes the shape. "static" symbolizes the qualities of strength, steadfastness and trust while "dynamic" symbolizes lightness, flexibility and vision in career.

The final work is now easily and widely applied throughout the University of Culture's identification systems, the combination of the letters V and H has created the shape of a book flower that is always blooming upward, high on a horizon of human knowledge (Figure 4).

The largest wildlife conservation and care park in Vietnam belonging to Vingroup, named Vinpearl Safari, officially opened at the end of 2015 in Ganh Dau commune, the northernmost tip of Phu Quoc with 500 hectares and 3,000 individuals of 150 species, built according to a semi-wild model, rare animals are cared for and protected in an open natural environment, this is one of the events of Vingroup corporation towards "National Tourism Year". 2016 - Phu Quoc - Mekong Delta" as well as contributing to promoting Phu Quoc tourism.

One of the top priorities given to Vinpearl Safari Phu Quoc is how to create a brand image that fully meets the criteria of wilderness, the immensity of nature and the rich vegetation in the area. The development of animal species, in addition to its main function as an exhibition park, is also a center for research, conservation and breeding of animals and plants. The experienced design team of Bratus advertising company has based on a methodical process, initially researching successful zoo brand designs in the world, from which they can create Summarizing and distilling the most quintessential details as well as combining creativity to create a unique identity for Vinpearl Phu Quoc (Figure 5).

With the desire to express the spirit of breaking all barriers, people and nature in harmony with humanity in the safari model, designers now want to change the way animals kept in cages are viewed in pictures. brand image, creating images of friendly, playful mascots. Based on consensus opinions, Bratus designers created hundreds of different sketches drawn entirely by hand. This is an extremely important process in designing a brand logo.

Hand-drawn works are always controlled by the artistic mind of an artist and the principles of a designer, the drawings are not constrained, ideas flow from the tip of the pen but still adhere to Comply with the principles set forth by the required brand criteria, meet the customer target and the applicability and feasibility of the product when it comes to market. The final work chosen by the design team is a blend of many different elements including the overall layout to create an image of Phu Quoc map with its own identity, not confused with other islands. another island, combined with a GPS positioning icon, along with stylized images of mascots following the minimalist trend. The mascots still clearly show the characteristics of each species but in the most subtle and simple way, giving viewers the most nuanced and meaningful feeling. Everything is arranged and nested to create a complete layout with the main sound being bird wings - the brand logo of Vingroup (Figure 6).

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It can be seen that the work is from the beginning to completion with most of the work done by the designer's hands, using the pencil as the main tool to create the initial sketch, after adding details and removing strokes. The excess pencil lines are refinished with a pencil to ensure sharpness and emphasis. Each animal is arranged in a complete circle and follows the golden ratio in the layout.

The finished works are mascots of different species, stylized in pieces, interlocked together according to the golden ratio, and when separated, they can be flexibly applied to the environment. In use, the font is edited from the Lithos font to bring personality and enhance the brand identity of the overall product (Figure 7), along with the combination of a contrasting color palette with the passionate warmth of the tropical region. Tropical Zoo has shown the spirit of a modern, liberal zoo. It also prominently promotes the image of Phu Quoc's identity, is suitable for the island climate, and is close to tropical people to attract friends from all over the world to come to Phu Quoc Safari in particular and Vietnam tourism in general.

Although it is not an official work, the combined work of a group of enthusiastic designers who came up with hundreds of ideas and carefully, meticulously and professionally sketched them has built personality and character. The image identifies the size of the parent company, Vingroup. The completed logo is a collection of images representing the Phu Quoc map, the positioning symbol and Vingroup's bird-shaped mascots and commercial logos with a new visual style applying a proportional structure. The golden rule and vivid, bright colors have truly brought a completely new face to Vinpearland.

Clear hand-drawn sketches of ideas help create Lotte Vietnam's online sales channel logo with elements of dots representing digital and people in a common shopping community, with the same system. Vivid colors typical of Korean entertainment (Figure 8). Long Van Group's logo is a product that demonstrates the completeness of the design when prepared from the hand-drawing stage, the logo is special, simple and easy to use (Figure 9), in addition to the company's iconic dragon mascot statue was also completely hand-drawn by the design team before being put into the finishing machine. Hand sketching also helps Gbox Studios have a special new face with components including the letter "G" of the brand name, the box shape and the camera lens forming a common whole with a simple shape and strong but still fully meets the brand elements we want to talk about (Figure 10).

5. CONCLUSION

In short, in Graphic Design, with the segments of brand identity design through logos, instructional design such as books, newspapers, magazines, posters, advertising design such as TVC, packaging, ... There are updates and innovations in trends every day, every hour. This requires creative movement as well as continuous learning and integration from designers. Equipment can be upgraded, trends can change, but the skill of an artist's hands and mind never goes out of style. Hand drawing always helps designers get out of the shell of their own ideas, bringing aesthetic values of ideas about layout, color, and shaping to achieve the most sophisticated perfection of the product. and sometimes hand-drawn products also become Graphic Design works instead of photographic images. Hand drawing applied in the design of graphic products today is both for styles that want to return to the classic, return to the most basic things, the original basis of design; can create something new, unique and more special.

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APPENDIX ILLUSTRATION

Figure 1: Old logo of Ho Chi Minh City University of Culture

Figure 2: New logo of Ho Chi Minh City University of Culture

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Figure 3: Sketch and new logo plan of Ho Chi Minh City University of Culture

Figure 4: Sketch and new logo plan of Ho Chi Minh City University of Culture

Figure 5: Hand sketch samples of Vinpearl Safari logo

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Figure 6: Combining ideas to create the Vinpearl Safari Phu Quoc brand logo

Figure 7: Lithos font

Figure 8: Lotte online sales channel logo

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Figure 9: Long Van Group logo

Figure 10: Gbox studio logo